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NEST InGrained ecosystem for zEroEmissioN buildings

D7.1 Initial communication kit

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
RP	Report
D	Deliverable
T	Task
WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

1. Executive summary

The deliverable *D7.1: Initial communication kit* is a public document of the GreeNest project, delivered within the framework of WP7: Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and IPR Management. A significant portion of the dissemination activities foreseen in the project relies on the production of high-quality promotional materials, showcasing project results and activities, which are then communicated to target audiences. The communication kit is a collection of materials created to support project communication and reach core audiences. It includes the project logo, website, promo materials, templates, videos, e-newsletter, and social media assets. This document represents an important step toward the objective of developing and deploying the GreeNest Dissemination and Communication Plan.

Initially, the project logo and visual identity were developed, followed by the construction of the project website utilizing the visual identity. The website is available online and can be accessed at www.greenest-ecosystem.eu It is designed to be dynamic, with the “News” and “Resources” sections being updated regularly and managed by the Dissemination leader (FENIX), based on the input from partners and project developments.

The deliverable *D7.1: Initial Communication Kit* describes the initial design of the project website and the project’s visual identity.

2. Public identity

The objectives of the public identity are to develop a design structure that can accommodate standard project identity elements, create an adaptable visual identity for various uses, and effectively convey thematic information when necessary. This includes ensuring immediate recognition of the GreenNest project through standardized communication templates designed for external audiences. Additionally, specific guidelines and structures related to the project, such as a definite set of colours and/or typography were developed. These guidelines will be applied to templates that are easy for project partners to adapt, understand, and utilize.

2.1 Project logo

The initial task for the promotional material design is logo development. At the outset of the project, FENIX recreated the logo in vector format to establish and distinctive project identity. The logo was designed to be simple and yet recognizable. During the design process, it was crucial to ensure that the logo reflected current branding trends, thus remaining relevant throughout the project's lifecycle. It was imperative that the target audience could identify the logo at first glance, making it easy to remember and reflective of the project's aims.

FIGURE 1 LOGO HORIZONTAL

FIGURE 2 LOGO VERTICAL

Project logo can be used in the following cases:

- In all documents developed under the framework of the GreenNest project, in documents to be submitted to the EC (e.g., deliverables).
- In PowerPoint presentations to be used for communication and dissemination activities conducted by each participant within the framework of the project, as well as in all promotional materials.
- On the GreenNest website, and on the websites of the project participants, with a link to the project website.
- On the official portals/platforms links (such as ECTP, KETMarket-BIMETICA, etc.).

2.2 Brand manual

It is important to follow and respect the project's visual identity to maximize the impact on the audience. For this reason, a brand manual has been created, outlining the visual identity guidelines (colour palette, logo variants, typography, and applications). The logos and brand manual can be downloaded from the project website (<https://www.greenest-ecosystem.eu/resources>).

FIGURE 3 GREENEST BRAND MANUAL

2.3 Funding

As stated in the GreeNest Grant Agreement and Article 17.2 “Visibility – European flag and funding statement”, unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement shown in Figure 4 below.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information and must indicate the disclaimer “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

FIGURE 4 EU EMBLEMS

3. Promo materials

In the initial stage of the project, promotional materials will be designed to support communication and dissemination activities of the GreeNest project, as part of the task T7.1: Dissemination, clustering and communication activities. The promotional materials will be updated regularly following the project’s progression and will be available on the project website (www.greennest-ecosystem.eu/resources).

Additionally, a collection of templates has been created, for the Deliverables, Meeting Minutes, and PowerPoint presentations that will be used by partner internally. Should the necessity arise, additional templates will be designed for partners to utilize, maintaining consistency with the project’s public identity, such as a poster template.

Short-term work being considered at the time of writing this deliverable includes:

- creating a project presentation
- designing flyer and roll-up
- creating an introduction video

4. Project website

The GreenNest project website was created and launched during the early stage of the project under the domain www.greenest-ecosystem.eu. The webhosting and domain were purchased by FENIX. Google Analytics is used as a tool to monitor Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and was implemented at an early stage of the project (e.g., views, users, countries, languages, browsers, devices etc.).

Another KPI that will be tracked is the number of downloads from the project website (e.g., promo materials, newsletters). The website was designed to be displayed on various devices such as desktop, mobile or tablet. The information included on the project website is likely to be valuable even after the project has finished. Therefore, the consortium aims at ensuring that the website will continue to exist after the project funding has finished (minimum 4 years).

FIGURE 5 WEBSITE ANALYTICS 15/04/2024

4.1 Description

The website has been designed by FENIX and the main aim is to address the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have:

- What is the project about?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?

The website itself contains the following information:

- general information about the project
- partners details
- list of news

- all public material generated by the project
- links to social network profiles
- newsletter subscription

4.2 Home

The “Home” page of the GreeNest website contains basic information about the project. The upper part of the screen shows the project’s logo, links for the social profiles, and a navigation panel. At the top of the page there is the project’s title, short project overview (goal, funding and consortium) and links to other pages with more information. In the footer of all pages newsletter subscription, funding, social media links and privacy policy can be found, as shown in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6 HOME PAGE

4.3 About

The “About” in the menu navigation is currently under development. At the time of writing this deliverable, the About page contains closer information about the project and the project consortium, including the partners’ logos and links to their websites, as shown in Figure 7. This part of the website will be static, except for the case of a partner change in the project or a logo change.

FIGURE 7 ABOUT PAGE

4.4 News

The “News” page contains a list of news and events, which will include project progress updates, meetings of the project partners and important events such as conferences, fairs, and workshops. Short information about the most recent news is reflected on the “Home” page.

FIGURE 8 NEWS PAGE

4.5 Resources

The “Resources” in menu navigation is divided into two sections: Resources and Promo Materials. The page includes promotional materials of the project, publications, public deliverables, and newsletters and will contain all public materials that have been created and published by the project. Subsections and pages can be added based on the project’s requirements and progress at any time.

FIGURE 9 RESOURCES PAGE

4.6 Cookies

Cookies are small text files stored on a user's computer by their browser. They have many applications, such as: tracking users on a website, remembering user preferences, enabling auto-logins for returning visitors, and enhancing website security. The GreenNest project website has also implemented a cookies policy to help the site provide a better user experience. In general, cookies are used to retain user preferences, store information, and provide tracking data to third-party applications like Google Analytics.

4.7 Future work

Short-term improvements being considered for the website at the time of writing this deliverable include:

- Update information on the “About” page.
- Creating a “Gallery” and “Video” page.
- Updating the website content to reflect the project's progress.
- Adding "Cluster partners" section to increase the visibility and impact of cluster cooperation.
- In case of workshop organization by the project or joint organization with cluster projects, registration page and event info will be created.

5. Newsletter

The newsletter subscription form on the project website was created using the Mailchimp tool and is directly linked to the contact database, where all subscribers are collected for future newsletter campaigns in compliance with GDPR policies. The subscription process is designed as single opt-in with Captcha to prevent spam and fake accounts.

The newsletter will be designed by FENIX with technical contributions from project partners. The first release is planned at M6, with future releases scheduled every 6 months. Each partner will share the newsletter among their contacts. The newsletter will be directly sent to the GreenNest subscribers who signed up through the project website and will also be published on LinkedIn, the project website, thematic portals, etc.

6. Social media campaign

As part of the social media campaign, profiles on social networks such as LinkedIn and YouTube were created and linked to the project website. The LinkedIn profile has been actively used and updated weekly since M1 by FENIX, with contribution from project partners. Updates include general project information, progress updates, photos from dissemination activities, infographics, and news from the related fields.

As the project progresses, consideration will be given to paid advertising campaigns to amplify the reach of key posts and engage with the maximum number of target audiences. This may include promoting public workshop invitations, crucial project progress reports and other significant milestones through paid ad campaigns.

7. Conclusion

The online GreeNest website plays a pivotal role in the project's dissemination and communication strategy. It ensures the project's visibility, facilitates the distribution of the project's results, and promotes their exploitation. An initial version of the GreeNest project website was designed, provisioned and published at month M3. While currently consisting mostly of static content, it has been designed to address key questions that external visitors may have and will evolve continuously as the project progresses. The visual of the website respects the PLURAL visual identity and Brand manual – typography (fonts), colors, etc. The consortium aims to ensure the website's longevity beyond the project's four-year funding period, ensuring that bookmarks and published URLs remain functional.

All promotional materials generated adhere to the visual identity of the GreeNest project, ensuring consistency and coherence. These guidelines were developed to align with the project's progression and will be publicly available on the project website, utilized during dissemination events.

Further details will be outlined in deliverable D7.2 Dissemination and Communication Report 1 due in June 2024.

